

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Lab to Life: The Journey of Insulin Synthesis and Its Types

Sakshi Masaye*, Pooja Kashid, Trushali Mandhare, Kishore Otari

Navsahyadri Institute of Pharmacy, (Naigaon) Nasarapur, Pune.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 09 Mar. 2025

Keywords:

Insulin, Biosynthesis,
Disulphide bridges,
Regulation of proinsulin,
Regulation of proinsulin
folding, Types of insulin and
its role.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14995654

ABSTRACT

Insulin which is a polypeptide hormone that is secreted by pancreatic beta cells and is one of the important hormone for maintaining the blood glucose level. It also plays important role in maintaining the blood glucose level in the diabetic patients. Recent studies have showed that insulin also plays role in bone formation and attenuates in osteoporosis-related inflammation. Insulin structure consists of 51 amino acids, with chain A and chain B where these chains are connected by two disulphide bridges. Initiation of insulin synthesis takes place in beta cells of pancreas, with mRNA translation into proinsulin having 110 amino acids, on transfer of this proinsulin into endoplasmic reticulum it gets converted into proinsulin and after exiting from endoplasmic reticulum it moves into Golgi complex where it gets converted into mature insulin. Mature insulin is stored in the secretory granules until it combines with the plasma membrane to release the insulin. There are various types of insulin available in the market with different onset of and duration of action. This marketed synthetic insulin are called analogs of human insulin. Various guidelines are been proposed for storage and handling of the insulin. Also, the advancement in the recombinant DNA has made it possible for production of human insulin and insulin analogs by offering the improved efficiency, convenience and safety to the patients.

INTRODUCTION

Insulin is a polypeptide hormone secreted by pancreas, by the beta cells present in islets of Langerhans [1]. In 1921-1922 Dr. Frederick Banting pioneered isolation and purification of the insulin in the Toronto. Insulin hormone plays important role in maintaining the blood glucose level, cell growth, and helps in the metabolism and

is made of 51 amino acids [2]. Insulin is encoded by the INS gene in the humans, which is main anabolic hormone of body [4]. It regulates the uptake of glucose by the liver, skeletal muscles and the adipose tissues for the storage of excess glucose, where this absorbed glucose is then converted into the glycogen via the glycogenesis or fats via the lipogenesis [6]. As it an anabolic

*Corresponding Author: Sakshi Masaye

Address: Navsahyadri Institute of Pharmacy, (Naigaon) Nasarapur, Pune.

Email : sakshimasaye19@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

hormone, it converts the small molecules present in blood to larger molecules in the cell. Low concentration of the insulin in blood has the opposite effect of the same, where the stored glucose is utilized from the various tissues and muscles. Production of insulin is high when there is greater amount of glucose present in blood as beta cells are sensitive towards the glucose, they secrete more insulin and inhibits insulin secretion when glucose levels are low [7]. Excess production and secretion of the glucose from the liver is controlled by the insulin, where the concentration of insulin in blood also helps with the synthesis of the protein in variety of the tissues. If pancreas don't make insulin properly or the body does not utilize the insulin properly this can lead to the hyperglycemia. Which can result in type 2 diabetes [3]. As beta cells are sensitive to the glucose, they secrete insulin, where the neighboring alpha cells secrete glucagon that shows the opposite action as that of the insulin i.e. high concentration of glucagon when less glucose is present and low concentration when high glucose level is present [9]. The glucagon coordinates with the insulin to maintain blood glucose level, where insulin acts by the anabolic pathway and the glucagon acts by the catabolic pathway [1]. The glucagon helps to increase the blood glucose level by increasing the glycogenesis and gluconeogenesis in the liver [9,10]. So, the glucose homeostasis is maintained by regulating the secretion of insulin and glucagon from the alpha and beta cells in response to the blood glucose level [9]. Except diabetes recent surveys showed that insulin also acts on the other organs of the body and play different physiological roles like in brain, ear, kidney, bone, skin, and the hair follicles. Insulin also helps with the bone formation and also attenuates in the osteoporosis-related inflammation [8]. When there is absence of insulin or insulin activity this can lead to the diabetes, or the condition known as

hyperglycemia, which causes the high blood glucose level. There are two types of diabetes depending on the insulin secretion and resistance. Beta cells are destroyed due to autoimmune response in the type 1 diabetes, so the body is not able to produce and secrete insulin [11]. Type 2 diabetes is caused primarily by the combination of the two factors like defective insulin secretion by the beta cells of pancreases and insulin resistance by the insulin sensitive tissues [12]. Insulin resistance can be said as clinical state where normal or elevated insulin level produces an attenuated biologic response [13]. Type 1 diabetes patients along with some type 2 diabetes patients requires the insulin therapy to achieve the optimal blood glucose level. As far the subcutaneous insulin therapy is the main stay of insulin therapy [5].

Structure Of Insulin:

Initially it was believed that the hormones would be the small molecules, until the structure of insulin was found to be quite large [2]. Human insulin consisting of the 51 amino acids, structure and the chemical property of insulin as polypeptide was found in 1928, where amino acid sequence of insulin was found in the year 1952. So, basically insulin is a dipeptide having the A and B chain which are linked by the disulphide bridges and having 51 amino acids. Insulin has the molecular weight of 5.8 kDa i.e. 941.176 g and its isotonic point is pH 5.5 [1]. Molecular formulae for human insulin is C₂₅₇H₃₈₃N₆₅O₇₇S₆ [3]. So, in insulin Chain A is made up of 21 amino acids and chain B of 30 amino acids. There are two disulphide bridges (residues A7 To B7, and A20 to B19) that covalently connects the chains, and the chain A connects the internal disulphide bridge (residues A6 to A11). These joints are similar in all mammalian forms of the insulin. The strongly conserved sequence of insulin varies only slightly between species. Bovine insulin differs from

human insulin only by three amino acid residues, and porcine by the one [4].

Figure 1: Structure of insulin

Biosynthesis Of Insulin:

Biosynthesis of insulin initiates with mRNA translation in the preproinsulin, which is a polypeptide having 110 amino acids with N terminal that is signal peptide, followed by the B chain then Connecting peptide (C peptide) and last C terminal as A chain (Fig. no. 2). On transfer of preproinsulin into the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) the signal peptide gets removed, and therefore converts the preproinsulin into the proinsulin, where the disulphide bond is formed between chain B and chain A. For the exit from ER the proinsulin moves through the Golgi complex towards the Trans Golgi network (TGN) to get divided into membrane enclosed organelles termed as secretory granules [1]. So, the division of C peptide in this compartment converts the

proinsulin into the mature insulin having only Chain A and Chain B [2]. Mature insulin is stored in the secretory granules until it combines with the plasma membrane to release the insulin, or are degraded intracellularly by the autophagy or delivered directly to the lysosomes, other words describe as crinophagy [2,3]. Newly synthesized insulin is superiorly secreted [4,5]. Although multiple factors are involved in the biosynthesis of the insulin, metabolism of glucose is one of the important physiological events that stimulates the insulin gene transcription and m RNA translation [6].

Transcription and translation of insulin mRNA is regulated by the glucose. 20 folds increase in insulin levels is seen in glucose stimulated beta cells of pancreas [7,8].

Figure 2: Biosynthesis of insulin

Regulation of preproinsulin mRNA stability:

The long half-life of preproinsulin mRNA is regulated by the conserved polypyrimidine tract and a UUGAAA- motif in its 3' – UTR [9,11]. Preproinsulin mRNA stability is increased two to threefold by the rousing glucose levels, compared to the non-stimulated beta cells. Polypyrimidine tract binding protein 1 (PTBP1) is the best-known RNA binding protein that regulates the stability of the preproinsulin mRNA [12,13]. This PTBP1 binds to the 3' – UTR of preproinsulin and avoids destabilization by opposing the T cell restricted intracellular antigen 1 related protein (TIAR) [14]. Glucagon like-protein 1 (GLP 1), which is released by nutrients stimulated L cells in gut, also helps in enhancing the stability of preproinsulin mRNA. Protein kinase A (PKA) mediated phosphorylation is induced when beta cells get exposed to GLP-1 [15], hnRNP K [12,14], hnRNP C, hnRNP E [12], hnRNP L, hnRNP U, HuD and poly(rC)- binding proteins (PCBP) 1,2 and 3 are the other preproinsulin RBPs present in the insulinoma cells [14]. Their involvement in the stability of preproinsulin mRNA is unknown [16]. The stability of preproinsulin mRNA is not expected to be affected in the type 2 diabetes, as the levels of preproinsulin mRNA in individual do not differ in type 2 diabetes and normoglycemia [17,18].

Regulation of preproinsulin mRNA translation:

Translation starts with binding of various initiation factors with 5'-UTR of mature mRNAs, in mammalian cells. This binding occurs in the specified manner and assists in placing large and small ribosomal subunits. On glucose stimulation the polysomes that stores preproinsulin mRNA in beta cells, are transported to ER, where the translation of preproinsulin starts immediately [19]. Along with the common regulators of translation, other specific factors regulate insulin translation with response to the nutrients, where ATP-dependent RNA helicase DEAD- box helicase

1(DDX-1) bind to the eukaryotic initiation factor (eIF)3a and eIF4b and to preproinsulin mRNA [20]. These results can be useful in pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes, which is often linked with hyperlipidemia; saturated NEFAs, like palmitate increases the secretion of insulin [21]. And exposure of ER to palmitate causes the depletion in Ca^{2+} levels and causes the impairing in proinsulin folding and ER stress, further decreasing the insulin biosynthesis [22]. Translating ribosomes receives the amino acids from the transfer RNAs (tRNAs), and their post transcriptional methylation enhances the constancy and, efficiency of translation. Glucose intolerance due to impaired insulin synthesis can cause the mutation or polymorphism in the tRNA methyltransferases, like CDKAL1 and TRMT10A [23-25]. In case of TRMT10A it causes a young onset diabetes that is correlated with microencephaly and intellectual disability [25]. All eukaryotic mRNAs are capped at 5'-UTR and are translated in cap-dependent manner, sometimes cap-independent translation can occur due to placing of initiation factor closer to the first AUG codon by internal ribosome entry site (IRES). By avoiding control for cap-dependent translation, cap-independent translation permits the protein synthesis in conditions where the former is compromised, for example, upon conditions like hypoxia, irradiation, apoptosis or amino acid starvation. Cap-independent manner can be used for translating the mRNAs for insulin and other secretory granules, thus allowing their continuous production even in stress condition [15], and upon mTOR pathway inhibition [26]. Polypyrimidine tract-binding protein 1 (PTBP 1) is the key for this process, who's binding to preproinsulin mRNA 5'-UTR increases the temporary hyperglycemia. Though longer exposure of human islets to hyperglycemia overpowers the PTBP 1 expression and insulin biosynthesis, this can be possibly due

to upregulation of microRNA (miR)-133a that bind to 3'-UTR of the PTBP1 mRNA [27].

The hinderance in the folding at ER is due to the mutations in the insulin's amino acid sequence, [28,29] that can be single point mutations or extensive exon deletion that can affects its translation. In such conditions the translation initiation of preproinsulin is seized, which leads to permanent neonatal diabetes. Translation initiation is also seized if there is mutation in the starting codon of preproinsulin. Impair ER translocation and target preproinsulin for proteasomal degradation also occurs if there is mutation in signal-peptide of preproinsulin, such as R6C replacement [30]. Mutations affecting signal-peptide cleavage, such as A24D replacement also causes permanent neonatal diabetes by blocking ER exit and causing ER stress [29,31].

Regulation of proinsulin folding:

Folding of proinsulin in ER is established by formation of three disulfide bonds, that are two interchain between A and B chain and one intrachain within A chain. Upon mutation of C96 in A chain caused due to alteration in cysteine pairing can cause misfolding, accumulation and toxic aggregation of proinsulin in ER which can lead to permanent neonatal diabetes or mature-onset diabetes of the young (As seen earlier) [29].

In vitro studies have suggested that in human genome of among 15-20 protein disulfide isomerases (PDIs) found, the oxidative folding of proinsulin disulfide bonds on conjunction with the oxidoreductases ER oxidoreduction 1 α/β (ERO 1 α/β) is facilitated by PDIA 1 [31,32]. For successive rounds of disulfide bond generation, PDIs are regenerated by ERO 1 α/β . Even the healthy beat cells show moderate amount of proinsulin disulfide mispairing and in early type 2 diabetes the accumulation of misfolded proinsulin intermediates occurs [33,34]. Thus, for proper beta cell function maintaining the proper redox status

which depends on continuous supply of reducing equivalents by cytosolic thioredoxin is important.

The antioxidative action of thioredoxin is inhibited by thioredoxin interacting protein (TXNIP) and this is elevated upon ER stress and insulin misfolding [35,36], elevation was also seen in type 2 islets [37]. Unfold protein response (UPR) counters the disturbance of proinsulin folding. From, the 3 UPR sensors, namely inositol-required enzyme 1 α (IRE1 α), protein kinase RNA-like ER kinase (PERK) and activating transcription factor 6 (ATF6), IRE1 α and PERK are involved in proinsulin folding [38]. IRE1 α is active under certain physiological conditions for oxidative proinsulin folding [38], whereas PERK is induced by ER stress [39,40]. Wolcott-Rallison syndrome, an autosomal recessive permanent neonatal diabetes is caused due to mutation in PERK [39].

Regulation of proinsulin conversion to mature insulin:

Two steps are involved in conversion of proinsulin into mature insulin; first, cleavage of C- peptide junctions at B and A chain at basic residues R55-R56 and K88-K89 (Fig. no. 2) [41,42]. C-peptide is released from protein convertase 1/3 (PCI 1/3), in human beta cells [43]. Second, dibasic residues R55-R56 at C-terminal end of B chain is removed by exopeptidase carboxypeptidase E/H (CPE) (fig. no.2) [41,42]. While elevated proinsulin secretion along with impaired proinsulin conversion is the hallmark for type 2 [44] and type 1 diabetes [45].

Genetic variants that affect the junction between the C-peptide and A chain, such as replacement of R89 [29], or the proteolytic activities of either PC 1/3 or CPE [46] have also been found in few individuals with type 2 diabetes and altered glucose metabolism. Mature insulin is stored in secretory granules, in most of the mammalian beta cells including humans in the form of hexamer of three dimers each of which coordinates the binding of Zn²⁺ molecule to H34 (B10) in B chain (fig. no. 2). Although guinea pig insulin is exception to this

as it does not bind to Zn²⁺. Zinc transporter 8 (ZT8) mediates the transport of Zn²⁺ in the secretory granules, where ZT8 is known autoantigen for type 1 diabetes and a risk gene for type 2 diabetes. Depletion in Zn²⁺ impairs insulin crystallization and insulin secretion in mice [47]. Proinsulin is converted to insulin by carriers of ZnT8 variants R325W that correlates with lower expression of transporter and have low chances of developing type 2 diabetes. Where in such individuals the import of Zn²⁺ in secretory granules is made by other zinc transporters [48,49].

Types Of Insulin Available:

There are different type of insulin available in market and each type works at different “onset” time, and its effects last for different time length, known as “duration. Peak is observed when the insulin shows the strongest effect. After peak, the effect of insulin wears off over the next few hours and so. Table below shows the type of insulin, how fast it starts to work (onset), when they reach peak level and how long it lasts (duration).

Figure.3: Types of insulin

Insulin analogs are the analogs that have been designed to mimic the body’s natural pattern of releasing insulin. This synthetic made insulin are called analogs of human insulin. However, the minor structural or amino acid changes in them

give them the desirable characteristic when injected under the skin. Some of the examples of insulin analogs are mentioned below in the table along with their characteristic features.

Table No. 1: Types of insulin their brand name and duration of action

Category/Name of insulin	Brand name (manufacturer)	Alteration	Preparations available	Onset time	Peak action	Duration of action
Short-Acting						
Regular Human	Humulin R (Lilly) Novolin R (Novo Nordisk)	-	Vial Vial	~30 min.	1.5-3.5 hrs.	7-8 hrs.
Rapid-Acting						
Insulin Lispro	Humalog (Lilly) Amdelog (Sanofi) Lyumjev (Lilly)	Reversal of amino acid proline at B28 and lysine at B29.	Vial, Cartridge, pen	~15 min.	30–70 min.	2–5 hrs.
Insulin Aspart	Novolog, Novorapid, Flasp (Novo Nordisk)	Replacing proline at B 28 with aspartic acid.	Vial, Cartridge, pen	10–20 min.	1–3 hrs.	3–5 hrs.

Insulin Glulisine	Apidra (Sanofi-Aventis)	Replacing asparagine with lysine at B3 and glutamic acid with lysine at B29.	Vial, pen	10-29 min.	~55 min.	~6 hrs.
Technosphere Insulin	Afreeza	-	Inhaler	-	-	-
Intermediate-Acting						
NPH	Humulin N (Lilly) Novolin R (Novo Nordisk)	Neutral protaminated insulin.	Vial, pen	1.5-4 hrs.	2.8-1.3 hrs.	Up to 24 hrs.
Long-Acting						
Insulin Detemir	Levemir (Novo Nordisk)	Myristic acid acylation to the lysine residue on position B-29 and Deletion of threonine from B30.	Vial, pen	1-2 hrs.	6-8 hrs.	Up to 24 hrs.
Insulin Glargine	Lantus (Sanofi-Aventis) Basaglar (Lilly) Toujeo (Sanofi-Aventis)	Asparagine replaced with glycine at A21 and two arginine amino acids added at position B31 and B32	Vial, cartridge, pen	1-3 hrs.	No peak	Up to 24 hrs.
Insulin Deludec	Tresiba (Novo Nordisk)	Deletion of threonine at B30 and addition of 16-carbon fatty acid to lysine at B29 via a γ -L-glutamic acid linker.	Pen	0.5-1.5 hrs.	No peak	Up to 24 hrs.
Insulin-Mixtures						
NPH/Regular Insulin 70/30	Humulin 70/30 (Lilly) Novolin 70/30 (Novo Nordisk)	70% Isophane insulin and 30% Regular insulin.	Vial, pen	30-90 min.	1.5-6.5 hrs.	18-24 hrs.
ProLispro/Lispro Humalog 75/25	Humalog Mix 75/25 (Lilly)	75% neutral protaminated insulin lispro and 25% insulin lispro	Vial, pen	10-30 min.	0.5-4 hrs.	Up to 24 hrs.
ProLispro/Lispro Humalog 50/50	Humalog Mix 50/50 (Lilly)	50% neutral protaminated insulin lispro and 50% insulin lispro	Vial, pen	10-30 min.	0.75-2 hrs.	Up to 24 hrs.

ProAspart/Aspart NovoMix 70/30	Novolog Mix 70/30 (Novo Nordisk)	70% protaminated insulin aspart and 30% insulin aspart	Vial, pen	10-20 min.	1-4 hrs.	Up to 24 hrs.
-----------------------------------	--	--	-----------	---------------	-------------	------------------

Guidelines For Insulin Storage And Handling:

Storage of insulin:

- Vials and cartridges of insulin that are not use in current should be stored in refrigerator (2-8 degrees) till expiry and away from freezing coils.
- Vials and cartridges that are in use should be kept at room temperature and should be discarded after 4weeks of opening. Action can be delayed by the cold insulin and may also sting.
- Always check the expiry on the vials or cartridges.
- Do not freeze the insulin
- Keep the insulin away from heat or strong light.

Handling of insulin:

- Before use the cloudy insulin should be mixed well. If someone is using vials, should place the

vial between palms and gently roll between them or move the insulin up and down.

- If more than required amount of insulin is drawn from vial don't squirt the excess insulin again in vial this may contaminate the vial.
- If using pen invert, it 20 times before use.
- Do not use vial or cartridge if it has reached its expiry date, the clear insulin has turned cloudy or insulin is discoloured, or insulin is exposed to high temperature or frozen, and when insulin contains flakes, lumps, or the other contaminants.

There are different methods for insulin delivery such as syringes, injection pens, insulin pumps and inhalers.

Figure 4: Methods for Insulin delivery

Role Of Insulin In Diabetes:

Insulin plays important role in treatment of diabetes either type 1 diabetes or type 2 diabetes. It helps to keep the blood glucose level in control and prevent the further complications related to diabetes. Insulin works similar to the human insulin hormone produced by the body. So, the role of insulin in human body is to control the blood sugar level and to store the extra glucose for the energy. If the person has diabetes, there blood sugar level keeps rising after they eat. That's because their body don't have enough insulin to store the glucose into the body cells. In type 1 diabetes the body stops producing insulin where in type 2 diabetes pancreas doesn't make enough insulin, or in some patients the

produced insulin is not utilized well by the body. Insulin therapy helps to keep the blood sugar level in the target range to avoid further complications like heart attack, stroke, kidney related diseases, eye problem, dental issues and nerve damage. In type 1 diabetes you need daily dose of insulin to stay healthy as your body doesn't make enough insulin. In type 2 diabetes insulin can be the part of therapy in combination with other anti-diabetic drugs to manage the blood glucose level. Insulin therapy can also be needed in the type of diabetes that is developed during the pregnancy known as "gestational diabetes".

CONCLUSION:

As insulin is a vital hormone in regulating the glucose metabolism, and its use in management of diabetes since its discovery has played an important role in many aspects. Understanding the biosynthesis and the structure of insulin has provided the various insulin formulation development for the treatment of diabetes according to the diverse patient's needs. And effective diabetes management requires a comprehensive approach, incorporating insulin therapy, lifestyle modification and ongoing monitoring. Also, the advancement in the recombinant DNA has made it possible for production of human insulin and insulin analogs by offering the improved efficiency, convenience and safety to the patients.

REFERENCES

- Rahman, M. S., Hossain, K. S., Das, S., Kundu, S., Adegoke, E. O., Rahman, M. A., Hannan, M. A., Uddin, M. J., & Pang, M. G. (2021). Role of Insulin in Health and Disease: An Update. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 22(12), 6403. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22126403>
- Lewis, G. F., & Brubaker, P. L. (2021). The discovery of insulin revisited: lessons for the modern era. *The Journal of clinical investigation*, 131(1), e142239. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI142239>
- <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/body/22601-insulin>.
- Voet D, Voet JG (2011). *Biochemistry* (4th ed.). New York: Wiley.
- Mudaliar S. (2007). Inhaled insulin using AERx insulin Diabetes Management System (AERx iDMS). *Expert opinion on investigational drugs*, 16(10), 1673–1681. <https://doi.org/10.1517/13543784.16.10.1673>
- Stryer L (1995). *Biochemistry* (Fourth ed.). New York: W.H. Freeman and Company. pp. 773–74. ISBN 0-7167-2009-4.
- Koeslag, J. H., Saunders, P. T., & Terblanche, E. (2003). A reappraisal of the blood glucose homeostat which comprehensively explains the type 2 diabetes mellitus-syndrome X complex. *The Journal of physiology*, 549(Pt 2), 333–346. <https://doi.org/10.1113/jphysiol.2002.037895>
- Davidovici, B. B., Sattar, N., Prinz, J., Puig, L., Emery, P., Barker, J. N., van de Kerkhof, P., Ståhle, M., Nestle, F. O., Girolomoni, G., & Krueger, J. G. (2010). Psoriasis and systemic inflammatory diseases: potential mechanistic links between skin disease and co-morbid conditions. *The Journal of investigative dermatology*, 130(7), 1785–1796. <https://doi.org/10.1038/jid.2010.103>
- Koeslag JH, Saunders PT, Terblanche E. A reappraisal of the blood glucose homeostat which comprehensively explains the type 2 diabetes mellitus-syndrome X complex. *J Physiol*. 2003 Jun 1;549(Pt 2):333-46. <https://doi.org/10.1038/jid.2010.103>
- Stryer L (1995). *Biochemistry* (Fourth ed.). New York: W.H. Freeman and Company. pp. 773–74. ISBN 0-7167-2009-4.
- American Society of Health-System Pharmacists (1 February 2009). "Insulin Injection [". *PubMed Health*. National Center for Biotechnology Information, U.S. National Library of Medicine. Retrieved 12 October 2012.
- Roden, M.; Shulman, G.I. The integrative biology of type 2 diabetes. *Nature* 2019, 576, 51-60.
- Cefalu W. T. (2001). Insulin resistance: cellular and clinical concepts. *Experimental biology and medicine* (Maywood, N.J.), 226(1), 13–26. <https://doi.org/10.1177/153537020122600103>
- Edwards C. M. B. (2004). *International Textbook of Diabetes Mellitus*. *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 97(11), 554. pg. no. 899-928.
- Weiss, M., Steiner, D. F., & Philipson, L. H. (2014). *Insulin Biosynthesis, Secretion,*

- Structure, and Structure-Activity Relationships. In K. R. Feingold (Eds.) et. al., Endotext. MDText.com, Inc.
16. "Insulin human". PubChem. Retrieved 26 February 2019.
 17. Fu, Z., Gilbert, E. R., & Liu, D. (2013). Regulation of insulin synthesis and secretion and pancreatic Beta-cell dysfunction in diabetes. *Current diabetes reviews*, 9(1), 25–53.
 18. Arvan P, Halban PA. Sorting ourselves out: seeking consensus on trafficking in the beta-cell. *Traffic*. 2004 Jan;5(1):53-61. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0854.2004.00152.x.
 19. Lee YH, Kim J, Park K, Lee MS. β -cell autophagy: Mechanism and role in β -cell dysfunction. *Mol Metab*. 2019 Sep;27S(Suppl): S92-S103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molmet.2019.06.014>.
 20. Goginashvili, A., Zhang, Z., Erbs, E., Spiegelhalter, C., Kessler, P., Mihlan, M., Pasquier, A., Krupina, K., Schieber, N., Cinque, L., Morvan, J., Sumara, I., Schwab, Y., Settembre, C., & Ricci, R. (2015). Insulin granules. Insulin secretory granules control autophagy in pancreatic β cells. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 347(6224), 878–882. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa2628>
 21. Rhodes, C. J., & Halban, P. A. (1987). Newly synthesized proinsulin/insulin and stored insulin are released from pancreatic B cells predominantly via a regulated, rather than a constitutive, pathway. *The Journal of cell biology*, 105(1), 145–153. <https://doi.org/10.1083/jcb.105.1.145>
 22. Szabat M, Page MM, Panzhinskiy E, Skovsø S, Mojibian M, Fernandez-Tajes J, Bruin JE, Bround MJ, Lee JT, Xu EE, Taghizadeh F, O'Dwyer S, van de Bunt M, Moon KM, Sinha S, Han J, Fan Y, Lynn FC, Trucco M, Borchers CH, Foster LJ, Nislow C, Kieffer TJ, Johnson JD. Reduced Insulin Production Relieves Endoplasmic Reticulum Stress and Induces β Cell Proliferation. *Cell Metab*. 2016 Jan 12;23(1):179-93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2015.10.016>.
 23. Setyowati Karolina, D., Sepramaniam, S., Tan, H. Z., Armugam, A., & Jeyaseelan, K. (2013). miR-25 and miR-92a regulate insulin I biosynthesis in rats. *RNA biology*, 10(8), 1365–1378. <https://doi.org/10.4161/rna.25557>
 24. Guest, P. C., Baillyes, E. M., Rutherford, N. G., & Hutton, J. C. (1991). Insulin secretory granule biogenesis. Co-ordinate regulation of the biosynthesis of the majority of constituent proteins. *The Biochemical journal*, 274 (Pt 1)(Pt 1), 73–78. <https://doi.org/10.1042/bj2740073>
 25. Wicksteed, B., Herbert, T. P., Alarcon, C., Lingohr, M. K., Moss, L. G., & Rhodes, C. J. (2001). Cooperativity between the preproinsulin mRNA untranslated regions is necessary for glucose-stimulated translation. *The Journal of biological chemistry*, 276(25), 22553–22558. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M011214200>
 26. Evans-Molina, C., Garmey, J. C., Ketchum, R., Brayman, K. L., Deng, S., & Mirmira, R. G. (2007). Glucose regulation of insulin gene transcription and pre-mRNA processing in human islets. *Diabetes*, 56(3), 827–835. <https://doi.org/10.2337/db06-1440>.
 27. Welsh, M., Nielsen, D. A., MacKrell, A. J., & Steiner, D. F. (1985). Control of insulin gene expression in pancreatic beta-cells and in an insulin-producing cell line, RIN-5F cells. II. Regulation of insulin mRNA stability. *The Journal of biological chemistry*, 260(25), 13590–13594.
 28. Fred, R. G., & Welsh, N. (2009). The importance of RNA binding proteins in preproinsulin mRNA stability. *Molecular and cellular endocrinology*, 297(1-2), 28–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2008.06.007>

29. Magro, M. G., & Solimena, M. (2013). Regulation of β -cell function by RNA-binding proteins. *Molecular metabolism*, 2(4), 348–355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molmet.2013.09.003>
30. Fred, R. G., Mehrabi, S., Adams, C. M., & Welsh, N. (2016). PTB and TIAR binding to insulin mRNA 3'- and 5'UTRs; implications for insulin biosynthesis and messenger stability. *Heliyon*, 2(9), e00159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2016.e00159>
31. Knoch, K. P., Meisterfeld, R., Kersting, S., Bergert, H., Altkrüger, A., Wegbrod, C., Jäger, M., Saeger, H. D., & Solimena, M. (2006). cAMP-dependent phosphorylation of PTB1 promotes the expression of insulin secretory granule proteins in beta cells. *Cell metabolism*, 3(2), 123–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2005.12.008>
32. Lee, E. K., Kim, W., Tominaga, K., Martindale, J. L., Yang, X., Subaran, S. S., Carlson, O. D., Mercken, E. M., Kulkarni, R. N., Akamatsu, W., Okano, H., Perrone-Bizzozero, N. I., de Cabo, R., Egan, J. M., & Gorospe, M. (2020). RNA-Binding Protein HuD Controls Insulin Translation. *Molecular cell*, 80(6), 1135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molcel.2020.11.039>
33. Solimena, M., Schulte, A.M., Marselli, L. et al. Systems biology of the IMIDIA biobank from organ donors and pancreatectomised patients defines a novel transcriptomic signature of islets from individuals with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetologia* 61, 641–657 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-017-4500-3>
34. Taneera, J., Prasad, R. B., Dhaiban, S., Mohammed, A. K., Haataja, L., Arvan, P., Hamad, M., Groop, L., & Wollheim, C. B. (2018). Silencing of the FTO gene inhibits insulin secretion: An in vitro study using GRINCH cells. *Molecular and cellular endocrinology*, 472, 10–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2018.06.003>
35. Greenman, I. C., Gomez, E., Moore, C. E., & Herbert, T. P. (2005). The selective recruitment of mRNA to the ER and an increase in initiation are important for glucose-stimulated proinsulin synthesis in pancreatic beta-cells. *The Biochemical journal*, 391(Pt 2), 291–300. <https://doi.org/10.1042/BJ20050468>
36. Li, Z., Zhou, M., Cai, Z., Liu, H., Zhong, W., Hao, Q., Cheng, D., Hu, X., Hou, J., Xu, P., Xue, Y., Zhou, Y., & Xu, T. (2018). RNA-binding protein DDX1 is responsible for fatty acid-mediated repression of insulin translation. *Nucleic acids research*, 46(22), 12052–12066. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gky867>
37. Bollheimer, L. C., Skelly, R. H., Chester, M. W., McGarry, J. D., & Rhodes, C. J. (1998). Chronic exposure to free fatty acid reduces pancreatic beta cell insulin content by increasing basal insulin secretion that is not compensated for by a corresponding increase in proinsulin biosynthesis translation. *The Journal of clinical investigation*, 101(5), 1094–1101. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI420>
38. Cunha, D. A., Hekerman, P., Ladrière, L., Bazarra-Castro, A., Ortis, F., Wakeham, M. C., Moore, F., Rasschaert, J., Cardozo, A. K., Bellomo, E., Overbergh, L., Mathieu, C., Lupi, R., Hai, T., Herchuelz, A., Marchetti, P., Rutter, G. A., Eizirik, D. L., & Cnop, M. (2008). Initiation and execution of lipotoxic ER stress in pancreatic beta-cells. *Journal of cell science*, 121(Pt 14), 2308–2318. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jcs.026062>
39. van den Ouweland, J. M., Lemkes, H. H., Ruitenbeek, W., Sandkuijl, L. A., de Vijlder, M. F., Struyvenberg, P. A., van de Kamp, J. J., & Maassen, J. A. (1992). Mutation in mitochondrial tRNA(Leu)(UUR) gene in a large pedigree with maternally transmitted type II diabetes mellitus and deafness. *Nature*

- genetics, 1(5), 368–371. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng0892-368>
40. Steinhorsdottir, V., Thorleifsson, G., Reynisdottir, I., Benediktsson, R., Jonsdottir, T., Walters, G. B., Styrkarsdottir, U., Gretarsdottir, S., Emilsson, V., Ghosh, S., Baker, A., Snorraddottir, S., Bjarnason, H., Ng, M. C., Hansen, T., Bagger, Y., Wilensky, R. L., Reilly, M. P., Adeyemo, A., Chen, Y., ... Stefansson, K. (2007). A variant in CDKAL1 influences insulin response and risk of type 2 diabetes. *Nature genetics*, 39(6), 770–775. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng2043>.
 41. Igoillo-Esteve, M., Genin, A., Lambert, N., Désir, J., Pirson, I., Abdulkarim, B., Simonis, N., Drielsma, A., Marselli, L., Marchetti, P., Vanderhaeghen, P., Eizirik, D. L., Wuyts, W., Julier, C., Chakera, A. J., Ellard, S., Hattersley, A. T., Abramowicz, M., & Cnop, M. (2013). tRNA methyltransferase homolog gene TRMT10A mutation in young onset diabetes and primary microcephaly in humans. *PLoS genetics*, 9(10), e1003888. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1003888>
 42. Krautz, C., Wolk, S., Steffen, A., Knoch, K. P., Ceglarek, U., Thiery, J., Bornstein, S., Saeger, H. D., Solimena, M., & Kersting, S. (2013). Effects of immunosuppression on alpha and beta cell renewal in transplanted mouse islets. *Diabetologia*, 56(7), 1596–1604. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-013-2895-z>
 43. Fred, R. G., Bang-Berthelsen, C. H., Mandrup-Poulsen, T., Grunnet, L. G., & Welsh, N. (2010). High glucose suppresses human islet insulin biosynthesis by inducing miR-133a leading to decreased polypyrimidine tract binding protein-expression. *PloS one*, 5(5), e10843. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0010843>
 44. Steiner, D. F., Tager, H. S., Chan, S. J., Nanjo, K., Sanke, T., & Rubenstein, A. H. (1990). Lessons learned from molecular biology of insulin-gene mutations. *Diabetes care*, 13(6), 600–609. <https://doi.org/10.2337/diacare.13.6.600>
 45. Støy, J., Steiner, D. F., Park, S. Y., Ye, H., Philipson, L. H., & Bell, G. I. (2010). Clinical and molecular genetics of neonatal diabetes due to mutations in the insulin gene. *Reviews in endocrine & metabolic disorders*, 11(3), 205–215. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11154-010-9151-3>
 46. Guo, H., Xiong, Y., Witkowski, P., Cui, J., Wang, L. J., Sun, J., Lara-Lemus, R., Haataja, L., Hutchison, K., Shan, S. O., Arvan, P., & Liu, M. (2014). Inefficient translocation of preproinsulin contributes to pancreatic β cell failure and late-onset diabetes. *The Journal of biological chemistry*, 289(23), 16290–16302. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M114.562355>
 47. Liu, M., Weiss, M. A., Arunagiri, A., Yong, J., Rege, N., Sun, J., Haataja, L., Kaufman, R. J., & Arvan, P. (2018). Biosynthesis, structure, and folding of the insulin precursor protein. *Diabetes, obesity & metabolism*, 20 Suppl 2(Suppl 2), 28–50. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dom.13378>
 48. Jang, I., Pottekat, A., Poothong, J., Yong, J., Lagunas-Acosta, J., Charbono, A., Chen, Z., Scheuner, D. L., Liu, M., Itkin-Ansari, P., Arvan, P., & Kaufman, R. J. (2019). PDIA1/P4HB is required for efficient proinsulin maturation and β cell health in response to diet induced obesity. *eLife*, 8, e44528. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.44528>
 49. Haataja, L., Manickam, N., Soliman, A., Tsai, B., Liu, M., & Arvan, P. (2016). Disulfide Mismatching During Proinsulin Folding in the Endoplasmic Reticulum. *Diabetes*, 65(4), 1050–1060. <https://doi.org/10.2337/db15-1345>
 50. Arunagiri, A., Haataja, L., Pottekat, A., Pamenan, F., Kim, S., Zeltser, L. M., Paton, A. W., Paton, J. C., Tsai, B., Itkin-Ansari, P.,

- Kaufman, R. J., Liu, M., & Arvan, P. (2019). Proinsulin misfolding is an early event in the progression to type 2 diabetes. *eLife*, 8, e44532. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.44532>
51. Osowski, C. M., Hara, T., O'Sullivan-Murphy, B., Kanekura, K., Lu, S., Hara, M., Ishigaki, S., Zhu, L. J., Hayashi, E., Hui, S. T., Greiner, D., Kaufman, R. J., Bortell, R., & Urano, F. (2012). Thioredoxin-interacting protein mediates ER stress-induced β cell death through initiation of the inflammasome. *Cell metabolism*, 16(2), 265–273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2012.07.005>
 52. Yuan, Q., Tang, W., Zhang, X., Hinson, J. A., Liu, C., Osei, K., & Wang, J. (2012). Proinsulin atypical maturation and disposal induces extensive defects in mouse *Ins2+/Akita* β -cells. *PloS one*, 7(4), e35098. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0035098>
 53. Chau, G. C., Im, D. U., Kang, T. M., Bae, J. M., Kim, W., Pyo, S., Moon, E. Y., & Um, S. H. (2017). mTOR controls ChREBP transcriptional activity and pancreatic β cell survival under diabetic stress. *The Journal of cell biology*, 216(7), 2091–2105. <https://doi.org/10.1083/jcb.201701085>
 54. Tsuchiya, Y., Saito, M., Kadokura, H., Miyazaki, J. I., Tashiro, F., Imagawa, Y., Iwawaki, T., & Kohno, K. (2018). IRE1-XBP1 pathway regulates oxidative proinsulin folding in pancreatic β cells. *The Journal of cell biology*, 217(4), 1287–1301. <https://doi.org/10.1083/jcb.201707143>
 55. Cnop, M., Toivonen, S., Igoillo-Esteve, M., & Salpea, P. (2017). Endoplasmic reticulum stress and eIF2 α phosphorylation: The Achilles heel of pancreatic β cells. *Molecular metabolism*, 6(9), 1024–1039. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molmet.2017.06.001>
 56. Sowers, C. R., Wang, R., Bourne, R. A., McGrath, B. C., Hu, J., Bevilacqua, S. C., Paton, J. C., Paton, A. W., Collardeau-Frachon, S., Nicolino, M., & Cavener, D. R. (2018). The protein kinase PERK/EIF2AK3 regulates proinsulin processing not via protein synthesis but by controlling endoplasmic reticulum chaperones. *The Journal of biological chemistry*, 293(14), 5134–5149. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M117.813790>
 57. Steiner, D. F., Docherty, K., & Carroll, R. (1984). Golgi/granule processing of peptide hormone and neuropeptide precursors: a minireview. *Journal of cellular biochemistry*, 24(2), 121–130. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcb.240240204>
 58. Chen, Y. C., Taylor, A. J., & Verchere, C. B. (2018). Islet prohormone processing in health and disease. *Diabetes, obesity & metabolism*, 20 Suppl 2, 64–76. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dom.13401>
 59. Ramzy, A., Asadi, A., & Kieffer, T. J. (2020). Revisiting Proinsulin Processing: Evidence That Human β -Cells Process Proinsulin With Prohormone Convertase (PC) 1/3 but Not PC2. *Diabetes*, 69(7), 1451–1462. <https://doi.org/10.2337/db19-0276>
 60. Ward, W. K., LaCava, E. C., Paquette, T. L., Beard, J. C., Wallum, B. J., & Porte, D., Jr (1987). Disproportionate elevation of immunoreactive proinsulin in type 2 (non-insulin-dependent) diabetes mellitus and in experimental insulin resistance. *Diabetologia*, 30(9), 698–702. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00296991>
 61. Truyen, I., De Pauw, P., Jørgensen, P. N., Van Schravendijk, C., Ubani, O., Decochez, K., Vandemeulebroucke, E., Weets, I., Mao, R., Pipeleers, D. G., Gorus, F. K., & Belgian Diabetes Registry (2005). Proinsulin levels and the proinsulin:c-peptide ratio complement autoantibody measurement for predicting type 1 diabetes. *Diabetologia*, 48(11), 2322–2329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-005-1959-0>

62. Chen, H., Jawahar, S., Qian, Y., Duong, Q., Chan, G., Parker, A., Meyer, J. M., Moore, K. J., Chayen, S., Gross, D. J., Glaser, B., Permutt, M. A., & Fricker, L. D. (2001). Missense polymorphism in the human carboxypeptidase E gene alters enzymatic activity. *Human mutation*, 18(2), 120–131. <https://doi.org/10.1002/humu.1161>
63. Wijesekara, N., Dai, F. F., Hardy, A. B., Giglou, P. R., Bhattacharjee, A., Koshkin, V., Chimienti, F., Gaisano, H. Y., Rutter, G. A., & Wheeler, M. B. (2010). Beta cell-specific Znt8 deletion in mice causes marked defects in insulin processing, crystallisation and secretion. *Diabetologia*, 53(8), 1656–1668. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-010-1733-9>
64. Rutter, G. A., & Chimienti, F. (2015). SLC30A8 mutations in type 2 diabetes. *Diabetologia*, 58(1), 31–36. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-014-3405-7>
65. Dwivedi, O. P., Lehtovirta, M., Hastoy, B., Chandra, V., Krentz, N. A. J., Kleiner, S., Jain, D., Richard, A. M., Abaitua, F., Beer, N. L., Grotz, A., Prasad, R. B., Hansson, O., Ahlqvist, E., Krus, U., Artner, I., Suoranta, A., Gomez, D., Baras, A., Champon, B., ... Groop, L. (2019). Loss of ZnT8 function protects against diabetes by enhanced insulin secretion. *Nature genetics*, 51(11), 1596–1606. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-019-0513-9>
66. <https://www.medicines.org.uk/emc/print-document?documentId=3513> (Regular Insulin; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017).
67. <https://www.medicines.org.uk/emc/print-document?documentId=34251> (Lispro; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017). [66] <https://www.medicines.org.uk/emc/print-document?documentId=25033> (aspart; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017).
68. <https://www.medicines.org.uk/emc/print-document?documentId=33165> (Glulisine; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017).
69. https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2009/018781s108,020563s091,021017s053,021018s0491bl.pdf (NPH; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017).
70. <https://www.medicines.org.uk/emc/print-document?documentId=32853> (Glargine; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017).
71. <https://www.medicines.org.uk/emc/print-document?documentId=14584> (Detemer; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017).
72. <https://www.medicines.org.uk/emc/print-document?documentId=27360> (degludec; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017).
73. <http://uspl.lilly.com/humulin7030/humulin7030.html> (Humulin 30; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017).
74. <http://uspl.lilly.com/humalog7525/humalog7525.html#pi> (Humalog 25; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017).
75. <http://uspl.lilly.com/humalog5050/humalog5050.html#pi> (Humalog 50; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017).
76. <https://www.medicines.org.uk/emc/print-document?documentId=859> (Novomix 30; accessed on 5 Dec, 2017)
77. Insulin basics. American Diabetes Association. <https://diabetes.org/healthy-living/medication-treatments/insulin-other-injectables/insulin-basics>. Accessed March 8, 2023
78. <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/diabetes/in-depth/diabetes-treatment/art-20044084#:~:text=Goals%20of%20insulin%20therapy,treatments%20don't%20help%20enough>.
79. Mantzoros C, et al. Insulin action. <https://www.uptodate.com/contents/search>. Accessed March 8, 2023.

HOW TO CITE: Sakshi Masaye*, Pooja Kashid, Trushali Mandhare, Kishore Otari, Lab to Life: The Journey of Insulin Synthesis and Its Types, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2025, Vol 3, Issue 3, 662-676. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14995654>

